

Mastering General Management

Developed by: TOPSIM GmbH

Article contributed by: Robert Galiard, TOPSIM GmbH

Keywords

Business, Controlling, Corporate Management, Financial Management, Human Resource Management, Marketing, Procurement Management, Production Management, Project Management, Strategic Decision-making

Figure 1. Graphic from *Mastering General Management*. Rights owned by TOPSIM GmbH; used here for educational review.

Introduction

Mastering General Management (see Figure 1) is a competitive business simulation that models the strategic management of a medium-sized company. Its goal is to make well-founded management decisions across strategy, finance, production, and marketing to ensure long-term business success.

The simulation is aimed at executives, junior managers, and advanced business students. It supports knowledge transfer in management courses and promotes entrepreneurial thinking.

As a serious game, *Mastering General Management* combines playful elements with realistic economic challenges, strengthening participants' decision-making and problem-solving skills.

The game mechanics are based on round-based decision-making: Teams analyze market conditions, develop strategies, and implement them across multiple business periods.

The simulation is built on the long-standing TOPSIM business simulation concept, which has been used for over 40 years. Version 15.1 of Mastering General Management was first published in the TOPSIM cloud in 2017. The simulation is continuously updated.

Facts

Release date:	Initial cloud release: Version 15.1 (February 2017); Current version: 15.7 (December 2023)
Developer:	TOPSIM GmbH
Game type:	Digital, hybrid (at least one team member needs internet access)
Number of players:	Optimum: 9–25 (3–5 groups of 3–5 persons each) per market. Multiple markets are possible. Player count is infinitely scalable.
Format:	Asynchronous, Hybrid
Time frame:	Approx. 16–32 hours depending on how many of the eight periods are played, how the simulation is run, and whether evaluations and additional activities are included. The time requirement also depends on the intended learning outcomes.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Device: Tablet, PC, or laptop with at least 720p. Browsers: Chrome, Firefox, or Safari. Internet access required.
Material:	Participants receive an introduction, a participant handbook, business news, and other seminar materials. Facilitators receive a seminar leader's manual. Short description: https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Mastering_General_Management_Flyer.pdf Blog article: https://www.topsim.com/blog/unternehmen-strategisch-fuehren-mit-mastering-general-management/
Price:	TOPSIM simulations are not freely available; a licence is required. Costs depend on the simulation, number of participants, and chosen usage model. Costs are calculated individually; inquiries should be directed to TOPSIM.

Resonance & Criticism

Mastering General Management is one of TOPSIM's most frequently played simulations and has been used for many years in educational institutions and businesses. Many universities successfully integrate it into their teaching (TOPSIM GmbH, 2023b), and companies use it in their training programs (TOPSIM GmbH, 2022a).

Participants and experts praise its realistic portrayal of complex business processes. Universities highlight their holistic approach, which helps students develop a comprehensive understanding of business interrelationships (TOPSIM GmbH, 2024).

The simulation's high complexity can be challenging. At the same time, it is considered an advantage because it requires realistic business decisions and encourages deep engagement with economic processes. No specific awards or exact user numbers are publicly available.

Game Principle & Process

In Mastering General Management, participants act as the executive board of a medium-sized company and make strategic decisions in production, marketing, finance, and human resources. The goal is to gain market share and secure long-term business success.

Participants analyze market conditions, develop strategies, and implement them. They have complete control over their decisions and receive continuous feedback through financial indicators and market reports.

The simulation strongly promotes teamwork, as participants work in groups and make decisions together. Competing with other teams intensifies social interaction and encourages the exchange of ideas and tactics.

The simulation is based on economic models from strategic management, controlling, and marketing. Instructors require some familiarization, which is supported by TOPSIM training materials and seminars.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Mastering General Management aims to achieve various learning objectives. Participants learn to make decisions under uncertainty and time pressure and to conduct market analyses. They develop analytical abilities by evaluating business metrics and adjusting strategies. The realistic representation of business processes fosters understanding of complex economic relations. Since the simulation is typically played in teams, it also enhances communication and cooperation skills.

The mechanisms support these learning objectives by simulating realistic corporate operations. Each decision directly impacts business performance, and participants receive continuous feedback through financial metrics and market reports. This iterative learning process enables them to learn from mistakes and optimize strategies. The simulation challenges and strengthens long-term strategic thinking and offers a dynamic environment that complements traditional teaching methods (TOPSIM GmbH, 2024).

Instructors serve as moderators. They guide the process, encourage reflection, and support participants in interpreting results. Generally, one instructor is sufficient, as the simulation essentially runs independently. TOPSIM's training materials, guides, and seminars facilitate effective implementation. Universities and companies integrate the simulation into courses and training programs to teach practical business knowledge and strengthen leadership skills.

Effectiveness

There are currently no publicly available empirical studies on the specific effectiveness of Mastering General Management. However, there is evidence supporting the effectiveness of serious games in education. One study shows that participation in a serious game can improve learning outcomes compared to traditional lectures (Eckardt et al., 2017).

Another relevant aspect is the flow experience, in which participants become fully absorbed in an activity. This intense engagement can positively influence motivation and learning outcomes (Hoblitz, 2015).

Although specific research on Mastering General Management is limited, general findings suggest that serious games like this one increase learning outcomes by enhancing motivation and engagement.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Mastering General Management does not include sensitive topics such as violence or drug abuse and contains no discriminatory content. However, the high complexity may be challenging for participants without prior business knowledge, unless instructors provide adequate support.

People with visual impairments may have difficulty interpreting the table- and chart-based data displays. The simulation requires strategic thinking and numerical understanding, which may pose difficulties for some learners. While business decisions are simulated, social responsibility is not a central theme but could be added in a didactic context.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Hannes Hamester

Sources

TOPSIM GmbH. (2022a). *Unternehmen strategisch führen mit Mastering General Management*. TOPSIM – Business Simulations | Learn by Doing. <https://www.topsim.com/blog/unternehmen-strategisch-fuehren-mit-mastering-general-management/>

TOPSIM GmbH. (2023a). *Mastering General Management* [Flyer]. https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Mastering_General_Management_Flyer.pdf

TOPSIM GmbH. (2024). *Planspiel als Unterrichtsfach: Mastering General Management an der OTH Regensburg*. TOPSIM – Business Simulations | Learn by Doing. <https://www.topsim.com/blog/planspiel-als-unterrichtsfach-mastering-general-management-an-der-oth-regensburg/>

TOPSIM GmbH. (2022b). *Mastering General Management mit der NOSTA Group*. TOPSIM – Business Simulations | Learn by Doing. <https://www.topsim.com/blog/mastering-general-management-mit-der-nosta-group/>

TOPSIM GmbH. (2023b). *Ganzheitliche Lehre mit Mastering General Management an der ISC Paris*. TOPSIM – Business Simulations | Learn by Doing. <https://www.topsim.com/blog/ganzheitliche-lehre-mit-mastering-general-management-an-der-isc-paris/>

Eckardt, L., Körber, S., Becht, E. J., Plath, A., Falah, S. A., & Robra-Bissantz, S. (2017). Führen Serious Games zu Lernerfolg? – Ein Vergleich zum Frontalunterricht. In *Edition HMD* (pp. 139–150). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-16742-4_11

Hoblitz, A. (2015). *Spielend Lernen im Flow*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-11376-6>